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SURFBIO: INNOVATION HUB FOR SURFACE AND COLLOID BIOLOGY
RESEARCH

Handbook of good practices for FAIR data
management

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PART I: KEY CONCEPTS

FAIR DATA MANAGEMENT

Good data management strategies are increasingly recognized as an essential element of scientific reproducibility, discovery and innovation. Researchers, publishers, governmental agencies, and funders increasingly demand data management plans ensuring the long-term availability and reproducibility of data supporting the scientific discoveries. This handbook describes a system for organising your experiments and your data following the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) guidelines for good data management practices.

Data management is an essential part within a project, thus data management plans should be prepared when wet-lab experiments are designed. A well-established data management plan allows proper alignment of the obtained results and their storage through allocation of infrastructure (space and funds) for storage and analysis. Moreover, structured reflection on data requirements can expose flaws in the experimental design, such as the lack of essential samples for the analysis or the inadequacy of the chosen controls.

In the first part of this handbook essential concepts related to FAIR data management are presented as well as general guidelines for good practices. The second part provides detailed examples and templates for implementation. In this handbook we will largely follow protocols, workflows and templates that have been developed for UNLOCK (Kleerebezem et al. 2021) and follow a fair-by-design approach to data management.

FAIR principles

The FAIR principles for handling research data were first formalized in 2016 (Wilkinson et al. 2016). These principles have been used to guide development of data policies, requirements for data management plans, standards and repositories (Collins, Sandra et al. 2018). The FAIR principles strongly emphasize the need of data being reusable by both machines and individuals. **Findable** represents the idea that it should be possible to find the required data. This means that data are assigned unique identifiers and are extensively described with metadata. Both data and associated metadata need to be indexed in such a way that automated searches can be performed. **Accessible** indicates that data should be stored for long-term and the ways of retrieving and downloading the data (and the metadata) are clearly described, with well-established access conditions and standard communication algorithms for

automatic access. In summary, accessibility implies that those entitled to access the data can do it. **Interoperable** links to the idea that data should be understandable, not only by individuals but also by computers. Thus, it is essential that data (and metadata) is stored in formats that are widely understandable and readable by humans and by computers. Interoperability also relates to the potential to combine datasets, which in turn requires agreements on the choice of identifiers and standards. **Reusable** ensures that data remains available for future research and that the limits and restrictions for data reuse are clearly described through appropriate licenses. Finally, reusability also requires that the data and associated metadata is complemented with detailed descriptions on how the data has been generated (provenance).

Note that accessibility does not imply availability to anyone and that not all FAIR data needs to be open. However, it should be noted that there is a trend towards open data and the current data policy from funders such as the European Commission can be summarized in “as Open as possible, as closed as necessary”. Therefore, a data management plan should consider if, when, how and to what extent data is to become publicly available together with the reasons that might prevent this.

FAIR data management for omics data in surface and colloid biology projects

Research in the cell-surface interaction field is being addressed from either a biological or a materials engineering perspective, usually based on trial-error learning approaches with limited outputs due to the complexity of this interdisciplinary topic. The application of both, state of the art spectroscopy and microscopy analytic technologies and microbiology and systems biology tools to study microbial-surface interactions can lead to a better understanding the processes occurring at their interface, which will contribute to provide ad-hoc solutions for novel materials design with enhanced properties, such as more durable materials (reducing losses), improved antimicrobial surfaces (for the health sector) or better microbial supports to increase the productivity of bioprocesses (pharma, food and agriculture sectors).

The need for structured data management has increased with the expansion of experimental tools and methods available. This is even more relevant for the study of surface and colloid biology. For instance, for the study of the development of microbial biofilms on a chosen surface multiple

technologies can be combined such as next generation sequencing (NGS) of DNA or RNA, GC-MS and LC-MS/MS, exploring the system at different levels (genes, transcripts, proteins, metabolites). Moreover, these can be complemented with techniques for analysis of the physical surface and its properties such as LC-HRMS or AFM-RAMAN. These are large and complex datasets; an integrative analysis is only possible if the information on how the data relate to each other is preserved.

DATA AND METADATA

Metadata is essentially data about the data. Biological and omics data often have lots and lots of information. Consider an experiment on which a sample is obtained from a bacterial biofilm, RNA is extracted and sent to sequence. As a result, one will have some fastq files (sent by the sequencing company) and some measure of normalized gene expression obtained through computational analysis. In this case these fastq files and/or the normalized gene expression are the biological data, but lots of additional data are available and need to be recorded to ensure that the scientific information in the data remains relevant.

Examples of these additional data that needs to be recorded are:

- Information about the samples (sample annotation).
- Phenotypic characterizations of the samples.
- Protocols for RNA extraction, purification and quality control.
- Sequencing technology and protocol.
- Computational analysis protocol, programs and versions that were used.
- Other computational outputs related to sample and process quality control.

In addition, relevant information describes the larger context of the research:

- Biological background of the study.
- Research question that was being explored.
- Main experimental factors that were under study
- Information on who did the experiment, who owns the data and who is the contact person.
- Publications related to the data.

All these data that describe how the experiment was done and the bigger context are called the **metadata** and it is essential that they are recorded. **Provenance** is a concept often used in data management and refers to the specific type of metadata that informs on how the data was processed.

REQUIREMENTS FOR PUBLIC DEPOSITION: MINIMAL INFORMATION MODELS

Public deposition of omics datasets has become an essential practice, enforced by journal editors, funding bodies and the overall scientific community. In addition, deposition on these databases is one of the possible ways of ensuring long term storage and data availability. Once a dataset has been submitted to a database and given an accession number, the data remains unchanged: although new versions can supersede previous ones, still the original ones remain available.

Public deposition requires completeness of the data, that is, there is a minimum of additional information (metadata) that is required for other researchers to be able to verify, analyse and reuse the data. Minimal Information Standards have been developed for a large variety of experimental techniques. Table I provides an overview of the minimal information standards for experimental types relevant for colloidal biology as well as suitable databases for data depositions. In addition, minimal information standards are also available for model annotation and model simulation (MIRIAM, MIASE) and detailed descriptions of these and other minimal information standards are available at <http://fairsharing.org>.

Table I: overview of relevant minimal information standards and selection of related databases

Type of experiment	Standard	Description	Example Databases
Any sequencing	MiXS	Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence	ENA GenBank GOLD DDBJ
Sequence reads: Genomics	MiXS; MINSEQE	minimum information about a high throughput sequencing experiment. See MixS above	ENA GenBank
Sequence reads: Transcriptomics	MiXS; MINSEQE	minimum information about a high throughput sequencing	ArrayExpress GEO

		experiment. See MixS above	
Microarrays: Transcriptomics	MIAME	minimum information about a microarray experiment	ArrayExpress GEO
qPCR based transcriptomics	MIQE	minimum information for publication of quantitative real-time PCR experiments	None (usually reported as part of a publication)
Metabolomics	CIMR	core information for metabolomics reporting. See also MIAPE-MS	MetaboLights
Proteomics	MIAPE	Minimum information about a proteomics experiment. See also MIAPE-MS for mass spectrometry	PRIDE

Minimum information standards contain a set of reporting requirements (so that all required information is included in the data and metadata) and a set of format requirements, as the data and metadata need to be converted to any of the allowed formats before submission, thereby ensuring interoperability. The second part of this handbook describes spreadsheet templates that have been developed to ensure that all information required by the corresponding standard is collected.

Finally, it is worthy to mention the Just Enough Results Model (JERM) available at <https://jermontology.org/> which provides a framework to describe in a general manner links between data and experiments. This is a general model that can be used to describe what type of experiment was performed, who performed it, and what was measured. For omics datasets we will see below detailed manners of implementing the minimal information standards, but JERM can be considered when other data types are generated.

Controlled vocabularies

Minimal information standards provide lists of information that should accompany the experimental data and format requirements for the data itself, however there is an additional key element related to how the information is delivered: the vocabulary. Free text entries are not limited but are prone to contain errors and typos. A controlled vocabulary helps researchers and computers to categorise information and reduces possible errors.

An example of controlled vocabulary is a drop-down menu with a list of countries (for instance when providing information on where the experiment was executed). Another example is the taxonomic classification of living beings where hierarchical terms provide information on different levels (strain, species, genus, family and so on). Controlled vocabularies are also often complemented with lists of preferred terms and synonyms so that we can easily associate concepts even if they are described with different words. Often these lists not only contain synonyms but identifiers in multiple databases that relate to the same entity, a typical example is the multiplicity of terms to define metabolites. For example, the InChI Key [ZKHQWZAMYRWXGA-KQYNXXCUSA-J](#); the KEGG id [C00002](#) and the MetaNetX identifier [MNXM3](#) all relate to the metabolite with chemical formula C₁₀H₁₆N₅O₁₃P₃, Adenosine 5'-triphosphate, commonly referred to as ATP. Inclusion of links to external databases helps enhance data interoperability.

Ontologies are closely associated with controlled vocabularies. An ontology describes categories in a given field; the objects in those categories and relationships between objects and between categories. Arguably the most famous example of an ontology in the life sciences is the Gene Ontology, (GO) (Ashburner et al. 2000). GO is used to describe the molecular function, cellular localisation and biological processes of gene products. It is designed to be independent of the concrete species and can be used to describe both prokaryotes or eukaryotes, and single or multicellular organisms. A typical example, that can be found at the Gene Ontology resource (<http://geneontology.org>), relates to the gene product “cytochrome c”, that can be described by the **molecular function** oxidoreductase activity, the **biological process** oxidative phosphorylation, and the **cellular component** mitochondrial matrix. The use of the GO ontology ensures that we can compare functional annotations of different organisms, for instance if we want to identify the gene products related to the same biological process in two different bacteria. It also enables analysis methods, such as GO enrichment analysis, to identify biological functions overrepresented in a set of genes (such as the ones that are upregulated upon biofilm formation). In summary, the use of ontologies greatly facilitates the comprehension of the content of a dataset. A large number of ontologies have been developed to describe biological processes and phenomena and some of them are described at <http://fairsharing.org> or <http://www.obofoundry.org>

THE ISA MODEL

The study of complex biological processes, such as those relevant in colloid biology, often implies the generation of multiple omics datasets from a set of samples that are related. It often happens that

we want to combine transcriptomics, proteomics and metabolomics data. For example, these data might be generated from multiple samples (and their corresponding replicates) some of which are to be considered as controls whereas others represent the effect of the phenomenon under study, finally the samples themselves might have been collected at different time points. Therefore, it is essential to keep the association between the datasets, the assays, the samples and the overall investigation, so that the context of the data is preserved.

The ISA hierarchy (Investigation, Study, Assay) is a framework for managing and pooling data corresponding to the increasingly diverse set of life science, environmental and biomedical experiments that employ one or a combination of technologies (Sansone et al. 2008; 2006). The ISA structure, builds upon the concept of **Investigation**, which relates to the project context and it is a high level concept linking multiple studies; **Study** which represents a unit of research and contains information on the particular research question and the specific system analysed; and **Assay** that corresponds to an analytical test that leads to data generation. Currently there is a growing ecosystem of public and internal resources using the ISA model and a number of tools (and templates) form the ISA software suite to enable application of this approach. ISA is supported by a growing community to ensure its long-term sustainability.

An extended ISA implementation

The ISA hierarchical structure needs to be further expanded if we want to keep detailed track of the links between samples, for instance when considering multiple RNAseq experiments from the same biofilm at different developmental stages. The UNLOCK infrastructure (see below) has developed the pISA implementation that builds upon and extends the ISA structure. This extended ISA structure is depicted in Figure 1

Figure 1 Extended implementation of the ISA model for data management. The Investigation, Study and Assay levels are extended with the Project, Observation Unit and Sample levels.

In addition to the investigation, study and assay concepts, the extended structure adds new categories to further contextualize the data. In this case, the top level of the metadata is the **Project**, an overarching research program with defined aims that can be related to a grant-funded program work. This category also facilitates the reporting as all work under the same project can then be easily retrieved. An **Observation Unit** represents an object subject to instances of observation and measurement. For example, in a study each entity patient, plant, animal, bioreactor, biofilm or area studied is one observation unit. When studying 50 different animals, each animal should become one observation unit. If multiple bacterial communities are grown to form biofilms, each one of them is considered an observation unit. From a single observation unit multiple **samples** can be extracted, for instance from different locations at a biofilm or at different time points (for instance to monitor biofilm development or the effect of a treatment, by measuring before and after).

THE UNLOCK APPROACH: FAIR-BY-DESIGN

UNLOCK is a Dutch national research facility granted by the Dutch Science Foundation (NWO) in 2020 with the goal to unlock the potential of microbial mixed cultures for a broad range of societal and biotechnological applications. It consists of four complementary, fully integrated state of the art research platforms; a Biodiscovery platform, a Modular bioreactor platform, a Parallel Bioreactor platform and a FAIR data platform (Kleerebezem et al. 2021).

Two complementary approaches exist for FAIR data management: FAIRification and FAIR-by-design. FAIRification is the step-by-step process of making data FAIR. This involves the identification and collection of datasets to be made FAIR; the analysis and evaluation of the data and corresponding metadata; identification and filling of information gaps, most often found in the metadata; transform if needed the data and metadata to suitable formats and standards and evaluate whether the newly generated datasets are FAIR. Thus, FAIRification is a retroactive workflow on which previously generated data are modified to meet the FAIR criteria. Instead, the FAIR-by-design approach is most desirable for newly generated data, where FAIR requirements are considered upon data generation so that no further post-processing steps are needed. The UNLOCK approach to FAIR data management relies on a FAIR by design data platform to maximize data reuse, focused on data ownership, intellectual property rights while aiming for optimal public data availability. UNLOCK activities on the FAIR data platform have delivered a body of tools for fair by design data management that are largely at the basis of this handbook and are extensively described in the second part.

ADDITIONAL READINGS AND ONLINE RESOURCES RELATED TO FAIR DATA MANAGEMENT OF BIOLOGICAL DATA.

- **SurfBio Webinar on FAIR data management**

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ONi7d649Z44&list=PLHXPvICcKh205cN7Ck5KKGsJLZq59UOqI&index=6>

Many of the aspects discussed here are briefly presented in that webinar.

- **Bioinformatics for the terrified.**

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/online/courses/bioinformatics-terrified/>

This online tutorial developed by EMBL-EBI targets experimental (wet-lab) researchers in molecular life sciences with little or no previous experience of using bioinformatics databases or tools. It provides a gentle and broad overview of some key concepts in bioinformatics. Following this 3h tutorial will allow researchers to get more familiar with strategies for describing data consistently.

- **Bringing data to life: Data management for the biomolecular sciences**

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/online/courses/bringing-data-life-data-management-biomolecular-sciences/>

Another excellent online course developed at EMBL-EBI. This series of webinars introduces key concepts in data management and how to apply them in your research. The course is aimed at researchers who are working with or managing data and those who need to create data management plans.

Both Bioinformatics for the terrified and Bringing data to life are part of a collection of online courses developed by EMBL-EBI providing an introduction to bioinformatics and to resources available from EMBL-EBI

- Goodman et al 2014 “**Ten Simple Rules for the Care and Feeding of Scientific Data.**” PLoS Computational Biology 10 (4): e1003542. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1003542>.

Some of these 10 simple rules built upon the practices we have presented here and will surely help you boost the impact of your data.

- Wilkinson, Mark D., et al “**The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship.**” Scientific Data 3 (March): 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

This is the work that formalized the FAIR principles. It is written in a general way, suited for all scientific data. Even though it is not a technical manuscript, many of the words and concepts appear technical at

the beginning and require some familiarity with jargon often used in computer science.

- Marko, P., Gruden, K., & Baebler, Š. (2021). Standardizacija in upravljanje z odprtimi podatki v biotehnoških raziskavah. Časopis Za Kritiko Znanosti, 282(49), 160–169. <https://dirros.openscience.si/IzpisGradiva.php?id=13837&lang=eng>

Describes, in Slovenian, aspects of standardization and management of open data in biotechnological research.

Additional information on how to create data management plans

- Michener, William K. 2015. “**Ten Simple Rules for Creating a Good Data Management Plan.**” PLoS Computational Biology 11 (10): e1004525. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1004525>
Highlights aspects to be considered, such as data ownership, roles, responsibilities and budgeting.

- **ELIXIR** <https://elixir-europe.org>

Elixir is an intergovernmental organisation that brings together life science resources from across Europe. These resources include databases, software tools, training materials, cloud storage and supercomputers. The goal of ELIXIR is to coordinate these resources so that they form a single infrastructure. This infrastructure makes it easier for scientists to find and share data, exchange expertise, and agree on best practices. ELIXIR is organised using a 'Hub and Nodes' model, where the Hub's role is to coordinate the work done by the Nodes, located over Europe. A number of materials are available on Data Management plans in Elixir. <https://elixir-europe.org/topics/data-management>

- **Data Management Wizards and Questionnaires.**

There are publicly available tools to help you generate your data management plan. These include questionnaires that help you reflect on some key elements. There are multiple such tools, for instance the one at <https://www.dtls.nl/fair-data/training/data-management-planning/> that also includes ample explanations on the whole process.

Other infrastructures and initiatives such as **FAIRDOM** <https://fairdomhub.org> work towards the development of communities related to Data and Model Management services and can provide assistance and useful advice when setting up data management plans for large projects.

PART II: DETAILED INSTRUCTIONS

The second part of this handbook contains detailed explanations on how to manage your data in a FAIR manner. In the first section, it is explained how to generate a metadata template that contains all the fields and information that needs to be recorded. The second section briefly describes how to fill in the forms and how to choose appropriate variable names for your project. The last section describes the way to validate the generated metadata files.

METADATA TEMPLATE GENERATION

As part of the UNLOCK infrastructure a set of FAIR-by design tools have been developed. Here we will describe the web interface available at: <https://www.fairbydesign.nl>. In that webpage, on the left panel there is a link to “Metadata template” that opens the web interface for metadata template generation. The web interface contains each section of the extended ISA structure stacked on each other and can be expanded by clicking on them. In this page you can define the key characteristics of your project and of the data to be generated and use it to generate an excel metadata template that will allow you to collect all the relevant information of your experiments.

The first three sections in the webform generate templates to collect general information about your Project, Investigation and Study and have fixed fields. When filling in this part you will be prompted to select identifiers, titles and description and those should be entered in the online webform. Please check the section on ‘Choosing appropriate names and identifiers’ to make sure you are selecting names with the correct format.

Project: This is the top level of the metadata. A project is an overarching research program with defined aims. For example, it could encompass a grant-funded program of work, in this way all data and metadata belong to a project. Minimum requirements are:

- *Project Identifier:* At least 5 characters max 25 characters.
- *Project Title:* At least 10 characters.
- *Project Description:* At least 50 characters.

Investigation: This is the second level in the hierarchy and can be seen as a high-level description of the experimental work undertaken. In addition, it contains information about who is involved in the research. It requires:

- *Investigation Identifier:* At least 5 characters max 25 characters.
- *Investigation Title:* At least 10 characters.
- *Investigation Description:* At least 50 characters.

One or multiple researchers associated with the investigation are also recorded:

- *First Name* (required)
- *Last name* (required)
- *ORCID* (optional): an ORCID is a free, unique, persistent identifier owned and controlled by the researcher that distinguishes her from every other researcher across disciplines, borders, and time. The ORCID can be connected to professional information —affiliations, grants, publications, peer review, and more. This ensures recognition of all your contributions. Read more at <https://orcid.org/> It is advised that you obtain your own.

- *E-Mail address* (required)
- *Organization* (required)
- *Department* (required)
- *Role* (optional)

Study: A collection of experiments designed to answer a particular biological question. This often corresponds to a research paper. Fields in the template relate to:

- *Study Identifier:* At least 5 characters max 25 characters.
- *Study Title:* At least 10 characters.
- *Study Description:* At least 50 characters.

In the following steps, you will be selecting which fields to include in the metadata template, so no more information needs to be entered through the webform.

Observation Unit: An observation unit is the entity that is being observed. This could be a patient from which samples are taken, a continuous growth experiment in a bioreactor or an ecological field that is sampled over time. At Observation Unit level you can select a “Package” of metadata fields that fits your Observation Units. The “core” package will always be included in the section as it contains the minimally required fields:

- *Observation Unit Identifier:* at least 5 characters max 25
- *Observation Unit Name:* at least 10 characters
- *Observation Unit Description:* at least 50 characters

Extra fields can be selected if they apply to your needs from the list of available packages and custom “user” defined metadata field can also be added. Add as many as you need as they will be added to the excel metadata template.

Sample: A physical sample that corresponds to an observational unit. The metadata of samples is subdivided into different packages to provide a means to standardize sample metadata. New packages can be created, or existing packages can be modified depending on the needs of a research project. Depending on the type of experiments different metadata fields are required (e.g. depth when samples are from the soil). The minimum information that is required for all types is in the “core” package that will create fields for:

- *Sample Identifier:* at least 5 characters max 25
- *Sample Name:* at least 10 characters
- *Sample Description:* at least 25 characters
- *Sample Organism, BioSafety Level, Collection date* (timestamp)
- *NCBI taxonomy ID:* NCBI provides many taxonomy ID’s also for (uncultured) species, communities, blank samples and synthetic constructs.

In addition, it is possible to select packages coming from the MIxS standard or to add user-defined fields.

Assays: Each assay type (e.g., genomics, transcriptomics, metabolomics) corresponds to its own unique sheet and new assay types can be dynamically added. Depending on the assay type different metadata fields are required (e.g., primers when using amplicon sequencing). In all cases a common set

of fields will appear as they relate to the minimum required information:

- *Assay Identifier*: at least 5 characters max 25
- *Assay Name*: at least 10 characters
- *Assay Description*: at least 25 characters
- *Isolation Protocol, Facility, Platform, Instrument Model, Date* (timestamp)

Select/enable the applicable assay(s) if you are planning to generate omics data from your samples. Again, there is the option to add custom fields. In the overall process of metadata template generation selecting an Assay is optional.

Once you are finished with the selection, you can click the button at the bottom “Generate Excel” and you will obtain the metadata template for your work.

It is also possible to add new Sample or Assay sheets to an existing Project’s Excel sheet at a later stage, for that use the “Export” button of the required Assay or Sample in the webform.

ENTERING METADATA

Upon completion of the webform an Excel workbook will be generated that contains a sheet for each level in the extended ISA implementation and will contain filled in information related to the project, investigation and study. This template is the one to be populated with information on the Observation Units, Samples and Assays from the study. These sheets are not limited to the predefined metadata columns, new columns can be added any time during the process. However, it is recommended to keep them within the available standards when possible.

Choosing appropriate names and identifiers.

Some general rules to be kept in mind:

- Do not start or end your filenames or variables with a space, period, hyphen, or underline.
 - As such, it is better to altogether avoid using characters that are neither numbers or letters, except for “_” (underscore). The reason is that computer systems often assign very precise meaning to these symbols. Examples of characters to be avoided: @, #, %, ^ (circumflex accent), &, *, +, ?, !, any type of bracket (,{,[,, and blank spaces.

- Most computer systems and analysis tools are case sensitive, so be aware that the same text combination written in upper or lower case letters corresponds to two different identifiers: “my_gene_expression_data” and “My_gene_expression_data” correspond to two different files and this can cause the not to be found when using search engines or tools. Be consistent with your choice.
- Avoid using generic names that match categories. For instance, don’t call a project “project”. Instead you can use “My_project_001”, “Project_001”, “Project001”, or even better “NameOfGrantedProject”.
- Consider that you will need to name files and variable during all your career, so make sure that the names are unique and do not match names/identifiers previously used.

VALIDATION

Consistency within your metadata is important not only inside your own project but also between projects, in this way data enables cross-studies. Validation of your metadata is therefore necessary to avoid common mistakes and to make sure the metadata standards are adhered to where possible. Not only can you check for mandatory fields but also mistakes for example that a study belongs to an existing investigation (typos). Standards should be checked by their predefined format, for example a date should be in the timestamp format (e.g. 2020-11-01T09:15:00) and certain values should be in “measurement unit” (e.g 10 mL).

Validation of common mistakes can be performed automatically by uploading your filled in Project’s Excelsheet at <https://fairbydesign.nl/validate> .

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